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UNPATH'D WATERS: Lands Beneath the Sea

Research Report: Work Package 3.3

January 2025

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Table of Contents

Lands Beneath the Sea: Work Package 3.3	2
1.1 Acknowledgements	2
1.2 The Work Package Components	2
1.3 Doggerland	2
1.4 The Sources and Collections	3
1.5 The Challenge	6
1.6 Methodology	7
1.7 The Simulation.....	12
1.8 Analysis and Observations	16
Bibliography	18

Lands Beneath the Sea: Work Package 3.3

This work package aimed to demonstrate how the deployment of a wide range of collections and datasets could make it possible to explore a remarkable ancient world. 20,000 years ago, the space between what is now England, the north-western European coast and Scandinavia was dry land. This vast space was marked by hills, valleys, plains, marshes, lakes and rivers, and was undoubtedly the site of a rich ecosystem inhabited by human beings. Over the intervening two hundred centuries, the combination of climate change and isostatic readjustment after the last ice age has seen the inundation of this now-lost landscape by the North Sea. Work Package 3.3 led by the University of Bradford sought to gather all the currently available information and create a simulation of this landscape which would be not only a key interdisciplinary research tool, but also a game-like tool to allow audiences to ‘visit’ the landscape at any time up to about 5000 years ago when the sea eventually covered it all.

1.1 Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Dr. Sarah Bradley of the University of Sheffield for her assistance with the BRITICE data set.

1.2 The Work Package Components

WP3.3 consists of two elements: the Unpath’d Waters WP3.3 Data Package (UW3.3DP) and the Unpath’d Waters, Undream’d Shores simulation. The UW3.3DP consists of an updated map of the submerged landscapes under the southern North Sea, with all available source data. The Unpath’d Waters, Undream’d Shores simulation consists of two accessible pieces of software which use this data as a base for a simulation of this land between the end of the last Ice Age (20,000 years ago, or 20 ka) and its final inundation (5,000 years ago, or 5 ka). The Exhibition edition of the simulation was designed for public spaces and formed part of the Unpath’d Waters travelling exhibition. The Home edition is a more detailed version of the simulation for home use. This work package was led by Vince Gaffney, with seismic data analysis performed by Simon Fitch and Rachel Harding and simulation design and development by Phil Murgatroyd.

1.3 Doggerland

At the height of the last glacial at about 20,000 years (20 ka) ago, when global sea-level was 130 metres lower than the present, 20 million km² of new territory was exposed around the world’s continental margins. The European continent increased in area by as much as 40%, exposing more than 3 million km² of new land. Once deglaciated, this vast territory persisted for thousands of years. In northwest Europe, the largest of these areas was in the southern North Sea and is often known as Doggerland. With an area approaching that of Great Britain, its coastal plains, low hills, lakes, river valleys, marshes, estuaries, shorelines and offshore islands, would have provided some of the most productive territory and resources available for human settlement and dispersal anywhere in the continent. From 16 ka onwards, progressive

global warming and sea-level rise transformed and inundated this territory. By 6 ka, these unique landscapes had almost totally disappeared.

Essentially terra incognita for millennia, investigation of these areas in Europe has generally involved the discovery and excavation of late Mesolithic and early Neolithic settlements and cultural deposits (c. 7–5 ka) in shallow water close to the modern shoreline and easily accessible to diver investigation. However, almost all of these investigations are very late in date, belonging to the final stage of sea-level rise. Even today we know almost nothing about the deeper, previously habitable areas of Doggerland and the communities that certainly lived there.

An alternative approach has been to model landscapes in the North Sea from seismic data collected by the hydrocarbon industry and from research vessels using higher-resolution methods of geophysical remote-sensing and coring of sediments. This has resulted in mapping and dating of much older (>8 ka), more deeply submerged landscape features, including major river valleys, coastlines, marshes and lakes. Over the past decades, researchers in the UK and Europe have pioneered such methods to the extent that we have significant knowledge of the topography and environment of the areas, but this is a landscape largely without people.

Even with these advances, we still have only tantalising glimpses of this underwater landscape. Moreover, ongoing climate change and the massive expansion of offshore windfarms and other offshore industries will intensify in the coming years. There is an imperative that the research community can provide better and more engaging methods to inform the public about the significance of archaeological landscapes they may not see or visit, to provide researchers with novel ways to interact with this data and to guide public policy on the location and management of the unique underwater cultural heritage of the North Sea.

1.4 The Sources and Collections

The data sources and collections utilised for WP3.3, which form a crucial component of the UW3.3DP are extensive and diverse. The following sections provide an overview of the primary sources that were instrumental in constructing the data package and developing the associated simulation models. These sources encompass a wide range of data types, including topographic, palaeoenvironmental, and archaeological datasets, all of which contribute to a comprehensive understanding of submerged landscapes.

12.3.1 Topographic and Relative Sea Level Data

The topographic and relative sea level data within the package are primarily derived from the BRITICE project¹, funded by the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC). This data, which includes digital elevation models (DEMs) and palaeocoastlines, was generated through glacio-isostatic models developed by Dr. Sarah Bradley at the University of Sheffield, and colleagues. Covering the UK and its offshore continental shelf, the DEMs provide a detailed reconstruction of palaeo-sea levels over the last 20,000 years, with datasets available at 1,000-year intervals (example shown in Figure 1). This data is pivotal for visualising the changing landscape and relative sea level over time and includes ice extent information. The datasets are

¹ <https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/geography-planning/research/geography/projects/britice>

publicly accessible via PANGAEA² and are detailed in key publications by Bradley et al. (2023) and Clark et al. (2022). Within the UW3.3DP, these datasets are formatted as ASCII files.

Figure 1: Example of palaeotopography and palaeocoastline (in orange) utilising the BRITICE data at 16,000 years ago.

12.3.2 Landscape Features

The landscape features layer in the UW3.3DP is compiled from several sources (Figure 2). The primary contributor is raw geophysical data obtained by the University of Bradford between 2015-2021, during the European Research Council-funded 'Europe's Lost Frontiers'³ project. This dataset is complemented by industrially acquired data, such as the PGS Southern North Sea 3D MegaSurvey, and data accessed through open access arrangements, including 3D seismic blocks from TNO (the Dutch Geological Survey), A15, and DEFAB. The 3D seismic reflection datasets are high resolution (meter scale), covering extensive areas and allowing for the imaging of large-scale drainage systems. Additionally, ultra-high-resolution Sparker and Parametric Echosounder data from the Europe's Lost Frontiers project provide detailed imaging of subsurface features at a centimetre to decimetre scale, though lateral coverage is limited due to budget constraints. These various sources, supplemented with shallow subsurface geophysical data from the British Geological Survey (BGS), enable a robust interpretation of palaeo-land surfaces.

² <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.945729>

³ <https://www.bradford.ac.uk/archaeological-forensic-sciences/research/europes-lost-frontiers/>

Figure 2: Data types utilised to map key features

In the UK sector, features such as channels and peat deposits have been digitised from windfarm reports and academic literature, with each feature referenced within the data package. In the Dutch sector, geospatial data for the aforementioned features has been sourced from the Netherlands Enterprise Agency (RVO) and included in the package.

12.3.3 Palaeoenvironmental Data and Dating

The palaeoenvironmental and dating data within the package have been significantly enhanced by direct sampling efforts, including coring and dredging conducted by the Submerged Landscapes Research Centre. Since 2016, over 80 cores were collected from the North Sea, ranging from the Doggerbank in the north to the Belgian Coast in the south. These cores, along with approximately 3m² of dredged material, have undergone various analyses, including pollen, SedaDNA, diatom, geochemical, and dating techniques such as radiocarbon and Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL). Data from these analyses, including core photographs and dating results, which have been published (Gaffney et al, 2007) or are pending publication, have been incorporated into the UW3.3DP. This data provides critical insights into the palaeoenvironmental conditions of the North Sea region. Additionally, dates obtained from windfarm reports have been integrated, pending any copyright or data usage considerations.

12.3.4 Archaeological Data

Archaeological data for the project have primarily been sourced from the SPLASHCOS viewer database⁴, which consolidates information on submerged prehistoric archaeology and landscapes across Europe. This database, established under the European Commission's COST program from 2009 to 2013, serves as a foundational resource for maritime archaeological data. Supplementary data has been provided by archaeological finds from the Submerged Landscapes survey work conducted since 2016.

The combination of these diverse data sources within the UW3.3DP provides a comprehensive tool for exploring and understanding the submerged landscapes beneath the North Sea, offering valuable insights into their historical and environmental significance. A full list of data sources used for the mapping component of this work package will be available as part of the UW3.3DP.

1.5 The Challenge

The main challenges facing submerged landscapes archaeologists are a function of the relative inaccessibility of the landscape, both to scientists and the general public. The main research tools used in submerged landscape contexts are the collection of physical samples and the collection of geophysical data. Geophysical data was initially only available as a by-product of prospection for oil and gas deposits (Gaffney et al, 2007). Since the Europe's Lost Frontiers project⁵ and the development of the Submerged Landscapes Research Centre at the University of Bradford, targeted data collection has been possible via collaborative research expeditions with the TNO and VLIZ. This has enabled us to direct geophysical prospection into areas with high archaeological potential. Physical samples have also been collected during these expeditions, yet the operation of a research vessel is expensive and can only be accomplished with the help of research funding and co-operative partners. Compared to terrestrial archaeology, which allows a number of low-cost methods of data gathering, bespoke marine archaeological data collecting is both complex and costly in both funds and resources.

The inaccessibility of the landscape also affects the audience for the research. There are no permanent residents of Doggerland who can identify these submerged lands as their homeland. This means there is both no natural audience for the research on geographical grounds and no automatic group of locals motivated to protect the archaeology that lies beneath the sea. Doggerland cannot be visited on school trips or as a tourist destination in the same manner as archaeological landscapes such as that surrounding Stonehenge.

With computer simulation we have a potential solution to both of these problems. Simulation can act as a virtual sandbox in which data can be integrated and scientific hypotheses can be tested, at comparatively little cost. It can also act as a means of dissemination, allowing users a glimpse of a land now inaccessible. It also allows a degree of freedom for users to focus on aspects that they personally find interesting. Simulation contains two advantages over the approaches used within different contexts within this project. A lot of what we know about Doggerland comes from comparative data from elsewhere. We find evidence of animals and plants in the physical samples taken from the seabed but the way that these imply a complete environment is derived from research on modern contexts in terrestrial landscapes. A GIS map of

⁴ <http://splashcos.maris2.nl/>

⁵ <https://www.bradford.ac.uk/archaeological-forensic-sciences/research/europes-lost-frontiers/>

data points, while desirable and useful, will only contain part of what we know about the landscape. A virtual sandbox is a dynamic environment in which variables and behaviours can be changed, leading to different results. This promotes the idea that there are multiple, uncertain, yet possible Doggerlands which can be explored virtually.

1.6 Methodology

12.5.1 Creating the UW3.3DP

Utilising the sources listed in the previous section, we have developed the UW3.3DP to help users access geological and archaeological data relevant to the southern North Sea, focusing on the Late Palaeolithic and Mesolithic periods (from the post-Last Glacial Maximum to the early Holocene). During this prototype phase, we maintained broad criteria for feature inclusion, aiming to represent features that likely had surface expression at some point between the Late Pleistocene and early Holocene. It is important to note, however, that not all features had surface expression throughout this entire period, and the mapping represents an amalgamation of palaeogeography over time, rather than a single moment in history.

12.5.2 Feature Layer

Various external datasets described in the source section were imported into QGIS, typically in shapefile or raster formats. When vector files were unavailable, key feature maps were georeferenced from reports or academic publications, digitised, and incorporated. For features identified in geophysical data, industry-standard geophysical software, such as S&P Global's Kingdom and Schlumberger's Petrel, was used to visualise and interpret the data. Algorithms (known as attributes) were applied to the 3D seismic volumes to enhance the visibility of geomorphological features. In areas with relatively flat strata, 'time slices' were used to create a bird's-eye view of channel systems, allowing us to digitise the external edges of key features (Figure 3). Where the strata were more complex, the layers were mapped, 'picked,' and made into grids, allowing attributes to be extracted. These digitised polygons were then exported as shapefiles, imported into QGIS, and integrated into the feature layer. We were able to interpret features down to a depth of about 70ms using geophysical data, including some tunnel valleys, which were reused by Holocene channels and likely had surface expression during the period of interest. For earlier periods, many of these incised features would have been deeper, as they filled with sediment during the early Holocene sea-level rise, resulting in wider and shallower features.

Figure 3: Example of the digitisation process using 3D geophysical data within Schlumberger's Petrel software, generously donated to the University of Bradford. The data shown is from the DEFAB block, open-access legacy oil industry data originally acquired by Fugro and available via the Dutch Oil and Gas Portal (<https://www.nlog.nl/en>).

The collection of external data, combined with the digitisation and interpretation of raw geophysical information, was completed in stages as new data became available. Each feature was merged to a single layer with a uniform attributes table and metadata. Attributes assigned include type, relative age, source URL, and access date. The final data package will be archived with the Archaeology Data Service.

This data package was used to develop the geological layers for the simulation. Since precise dating is unavailable for many features, they were combined into one layer and assigned an arbitrary depth of -5m, reflecting the average depth of channel features from the ERC-funded Lost Frontiers project. This depth is a general estimate—overestimated in some areas and underestimated in others. Future work will focus on assigning more accurate depths and ages to further refine the mapping. These features were then embossed (or burnt) into a zero-depth raster layer, creating a surface with negative features, which were added to the topographic Digital Elevation Models (DEM), along with the sandbank removal layer (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Feature layer with a 5m depth utilised in the simulation

Within the dataset, we have also digitised key academic contributions hypothesising the locations of palaeochannels and drainage patterns across the southern North Sea during the period of interest (Amkreutz et al., 2022; Garcia Moreno, 2017; Hijma and Cohen, 2011) (Figure 5). While these sources are included in the data package for reference, they were not used in the current simulation, as we opted to work only with raw, unextrapolated data for this version.

Figure 5: Comparison of academic sourced palaeogeographic reconstructions with the Unpath'd Waters feature layer. Background is GEBCO bathymetry utilising the WIKI 2.0 colour ramp to highlight areas which would have been land during the early Mesolithic at about 10,000 years ago (green) and which would be marine (blue).

Incorporating these palaeogeographic reconstructions from academic research enables comparisons between the latest understanding of channel systems in the North Sea and existing models. Future work at the Submerged Landscapes Research Centre will use this collated dataset to produce an updated extrapolation of the drainage patterns. This will inform future simulations and assist in outreach efforts by updating palaeogeographic maps of Doggerland.

12.5.3 Other Data Types

In addition to features like channel systems, we have incorporated data from both internal and external sources related to paleoenvironmental analysis and the dating of Late Pleistocene and early Holocene strata. This includes information on peat deposits, which are valuable for sea level reconstructions and for reducing risk in wind farm placement. These data are provided as point vector files within the data package, with hotlinks to relevant images, URLs, and datasets.

12.5.4 Removal of Modern Features for DEMs

Modern sandbanks are a key feature of the present-day bathymetry (Figure 6) of the southern North Sea. To more accurately represent the landscape prior to inundation and marine processes, these sand features must be removed to somewhat negate the effects of erosion and deposition that have occurred since the transgression of Doggerland. While it hasn't been possible to account for every small change due to limited data, future research will address this. However, where subsurface data is available—such as in the case study areas of the southern North Sea—we have been able to perform higher-resolution adjustments. For other areas, we have focused primarily on removing large-scale sandbanks and adjoining troughs.

Figure 6: Present day Bathymetry of the southern North Sea. The GEBCO Grid 2021 dataset.

This process has been carried out using smoothing tools within QGIS on the DEMs used in the simulation. These tools have been applied to smooth discrete areas without altering the broader gradients of the topography. The resulting ASCII files utilised in the simulation have had large positive features removed, and the surrounding areas have been smoothed to create a more uniform topography. Although this method is somewhat crude, it is a prototype that can be refined further and due to the low resolution of the DEM required for the simulation, (much lower than shown in Figure 6) this method works well.

1.7 The Simulation

The simulation is a virtual sandbox in which the user can navigate and explore the data from and about Doggerland. It acts as a means of data integration and visualisation as well as allowing users to focus on the aspects which they find most interesting. It consists of three screens: the intro screen, the regional map and the local map.

The introductory screen (Figure 7) serves as a welcome to the simulation. In the Exhibition version it gives a brief introduction to the project and the user controls. In the Home version it also allows the user to alter settings which affect the appearance and operation of the simulation.

Figure 7: The simulation introductory screen, Exhibition edition.

The regional map (Figure 8) shows Great Britain, parts of Ireland and the southern North Sea. It allows the user to move forwards and backwards in time between 20 ka and 5 ka. The position of the land and sea changes based on the base data and the method of interpolation. Glaciers are shown between 20 ka and 15 ka. This data is based on that published by the BRITICE project, with modern sandbanks removed where possible. On this map, the user can select a location and time for the creation of a local simulation of the environment at that point in space and time.

Figure 8: The regional map, showing the entire simulation area.

The local simulation uses the large scale, regional data, along with the features mapped within WP3.3 and a climate model to produce an approximately 13km x 13km area containing animals, plants and humans (Figure 9). The environments are based on the work of the Europe’s Lost Frontiers project, especially the sedimentary DNA analysis, which gives a more complex set of data than traditional methods (Gaffney & Fitch, 2022). Unless the environment is over 90% tundra, a single camp of humans is placed in a suitable location.

Figure 9: The local simulation, showing a largely forested environment containing some boar.

1.7.1 Design and Implementation of the Simulation

The simulation was implemented in the Unity⁶ development platform, due to the ease with which executable, robust code compatible with many Microsoft Windows systems could be generated. Unity is frequently used for the development of independent games and educational software and there are many learning resources available online. 3D models were created in Blender⁷, an open-source modelling software package.

The simulation uses a series of data files corresponding to the land surface at each 1,000-year interval between 20 ka and 5 ka, inclusive. These are derived from the files created by the BRITICE project, with a reduction in resolution and the removal of modern sandbanks the only forms of further processing. These are used as the base data for the regional map, with the addition of glaciers which were digitised from Clark et al, 2022. The data points around the selected location are passed to the local simulation and act as a base for the landscape, which is procedurally downscaled (Contreras et al, 2018). The features mapped within the data package are then embossed onto this landscape and a brief fluid simulation is run over the resulting surface to identify areas liable to forming wetlands or rivers. Depending on sea level, morphology and the results of this fluid simulation, the landscape is split into the following categories:

- Sea
- Intertidal zone

⁶ <https://unity.com/>

⁷ <https://www.blender.org/>

- Marsh/Wetland
- Grassland
- Woodland
- Tundra
- River

Trees are added to woodland areas and animals are placed within the landscape in suitable locations. Within the Exhibition version of the simulation, these are:

- Boar
- Arctic Fox
- Aurochs
- Elk/Moose
- Beaver

In the Exhibition version of the simulation, the animals and humans do not move or exhibit any other kinds of behaviours. Within the Home version, these animals, along with any human inhabitants, forage for food and react to the changing seasons.

1.7.2 Accessibility

A key aspect of the design of the simulation is the accessibility of both the software and the data. Itch.io was chosen as a distribution platform due to its position as a significant host of small to medium scale software. Software on Itch.io is findable and the interface is straightforward to navigate. The software itself is designed to be easy to install and use. It is delivered as a zipped file structure which only requires the user to unzip and run the executable programme. No other software packages are required, and the software can be used with either an X-box compatible controller or a standard keyboard. Both the font and colour scheme of the user interface elements can be toggled as an aid to accessibility.

Producing software that is easy to use lowers the barriers to interaction with both the simulation and the base data. Although the data package files are available in formats which can be easily loaded into GIS software for further analysis and integration with other data sets, the ability to navigate the collected data sets within the simulation allows users unfamiliar with standard GIS software access to the data. With one click to download the simulation, one click to unzip and a double click to run, the user can be looking at, and navigating through, the data with only four clicks. This has obvious benefits for uptake by the general public but will also increase usage among researchers, not all of whom have the technical skills or time to handle a GIS project.

1.7.3 Open Access Archiving

The GIS data within the UW3.3DP will be archived with the Archaeology Data Service. The simulation software will be available on Itch.io for the duration of the platform. The source files will be available from the Unpath'd Waters Github repository⁸.

1.7.4 Impact

The objective of WP3.3 was to see whether it would be possible to combine heritage collections (eg archaeological evidence) and non-heritage collections (eg geographical, oceanographical, industry surveys etc etc) to provide the best possible and readily accessible model for a lost prehistoric landscape. The impacts we have identified are:

- A more compelling model for risk assessment in North Sea development
- A better baseline for research into the palaeolithic and Mesolithic
- Increased access to the datasets via the Simulation
- Engagement with interdisciplinary researchers in associated fields (Quaternary science, sea-level studies etc)

The potential impact of accessible simulation software of this kind is hard to measure due to the limited number of comparable examples. The stand-alone nature of the software is deliberately similar to that found in the computer entertainment industry. Games with explicit or implicit archaeological content have many times the number of downloads of even the most widely used archaeological simulations. Rare examples include *Ancestors: Stories of Atapuerca* (Rubio-Campillo, 2020) and *Unreal World*⁹, both of which have been downloaded in numbers far exceeding the most successful academic archaeological simulations (e.g. Janssen 2009, including its precursor and successor).

1.8 Analysis and Observations

While the medium to long term impact of both the simulation and the data package are uncertain, the short-term impact has been noticeable within the research community, with users within and around the Submerged Landscape Research Centre using the software as a quick method of examining the changing land and sea levels of the southern North Sea. As an example of the type of work that Unpath'd Waters was funded to accomplish, the simulation is a novel method of providing access to a physically inaccessible landscape. It places cutting edge archaeological data in the hands of anyone with a desktop PC, regardless of location, educational attainment or cultural background. This approach to accessibility has the potential to widen the audience for archaeology across the globe, which is particularly appropriate to the field of submerged landscapes due to their global nature. Doggerland is only one of many similar lands across the whole Earth, whose relatively unexplored nature is likely to hide the answers to key questions of human development.

Although the accompanying data package is used within the simulation as an input, it is a valuable research output in itself. The data created as a part of Unpath'd Waters represents the most complete map of

⁸ <https://github.com/UnpathdWaters>

⁹ <http://unrealworld.fi/>

Doggerland yet created. This emphasises both the inter and multi-disciplinary nature of the project and simulation's role as a key data integration tool.

Bibliography

- Amkreutz, L., Cohen, K., Hijma, M., Odé, O (2022) Mapping a drowning land, in: Doggerland. Lost World under the North Sea. Edited by Luc Amkreutz & Sasja van der Vaart-Verschoof. Sidestone Press, Leiden.
- Bradley, S.L., Ely, J.C., Clark, C.D., Edwards, R.J. and Shennan, I. (2023), Reconstruction of the palaeo-sea level of Britain and Ireland arising from empirical constraints of ice extent: implications for regional sea level forecasts and North American ice sheet volume. *J. Quaternary Sci*, 38: 791-805.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.3523>
- Clark, C.D., Ely, J.C., Hindmarsh, R.C.A., Bradley, S., Ignéczi, A., Fabel, D., Ó Cofaigh, C., Chiverrell, R.C., Scourse, J., Benetti, S., Bradwell, T., Evans, D.J.A., Roberts, D.H., Burke, M., Callard, S.L., Medialdea, A., Saher, M., Small, D., Smedley, R.K., Gasson, E., Gregoire, L., Gandy, N., Hughes, A.L.C., Ballantyne, C., Bateman, M.D., Bigg, G.R., Doole, J., Dove, D., Duller, G.A.T., Jenkins, G.T.H., Livingstone, S.L., McCarron, S., Moreton, S., Pollard, D., Praeg, D., Sejrup, H.P., Van Landeghem, K.J.J. and Wilson, P. (2022), Growth and retreat of the last British–Irish Ice Sheet, 31 000 to 15 000 years ago: the BRITICE-CHRONO reconstruction. *Boreas*, 51: 699-758. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12594>
- Clark, C.D., Ely, J.C., Fabel, D., Bradley, S.L. (2022): BRITICE-CHRONO maps and GIS data of the last British-Irish Ice Sheet 31 to 15 ka, including model reconstruction, geochronometric age spreadsheet, palaeotopographies and coastline positions [dataset]. PANGAEA, <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.945729>
- Contreras, D., Guiot, J., Suarez, R., & Kirman, A. (2018). Reaching the human scale: A spatial and temporal downscaling approach to the archaeological implications of paleoclimate data. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 93, 54-67.
- Gaffney, V., Fitch, S., & Thomson, K. (2007). Mapping Doggerland: the Mesolithic landscapes of the southern North Sea. Archaeopress, Oxford.
- Gaffney, V., & Fitch, S. (Eds.). (2022). Europe's Lost Frontiers: Volume 1: Context and Methodology (Vol. 1). Archaeopress, Oxford.
- Garcia Moreno, D (2017) Origin and geomorphology of the Dover Strait and southern North Sea palaeovalleys and palaeo-depressions. PhD Thesis. University of Ghent. <http://hdl.handle.net/1854/LU-8536549>
- Hijma, M.P. and Cohen, K.M. (2011), Holocene transgression of the Rhine river mouth area, The Netherlands/Southern North Sea: palaeogeography and sequence stratigraphy. *Sedimentology*, 58: 1453-1485. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3091.2010.01222.x>
- Janssen, M. A. (2009). Understanding artificial anasazi. *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation*, 12(4), 13.
- Rubio-Campillo, X. (2020). Gameplay as Learning: The Use of Game Design to Explain Human Evolution. *Communicating the Past*, 45